

A Reverse-Osmosis Membrane : Thermodynamic Evaluation of its Effective Thickness

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In recent years, various studies, electron microscopy among them^{1,2}, have revealed that the cellulose acetate membranes, which have been successfully used in hyperfiltration (reverseosmosis) of saline water, are not homogeneous, and are characterised by very thin dense surface layers where the maximum salt-rejection takes place. Various hypotheses have been put forward to explain such rejection in terms of the failure of water to effectively hydrate the ions in this thin layer, and this is said to result from a change in structure of water (from bulk-water) inside the layer, due to its interaction with this dense layer, which behaves differently from the bulk-membrane phase. As a consequence, the salt is thrown out as a "precipitate". It is worth noting that the thermodynamic approach for diffusion also leads to the conclusion that the effective thickness of such membranes for water transport is indeed very small as compared to their total thickness, and this will be deduced in the present communication.

The membrane is considered, for the sake of simplicity, to be perfectly semi-permeable, i.e., only water can diffuse through it. The general form of Fick's first law for such transport process reads,

$$J_w = -D_w \frac{C_w}{RT} (\partial \mu_w / \partial x)_M \quad \dots (1)$$

where J_w is the diffusion flux of water through the membrane ($\text{mol. cm}^{-2} \text{ sec}^{-1}$), D_w , the ordinary (isothermal) diffusion coefficient of water ($\text{cm}^2 \text{ sec}^{-1}$), C_w , the "concentration of water" in the membrane (mol. cm^{-3}), $(\partial \mu_w / \partial x)_M$, the chemical potential gradient of water in the membrane (M), and this is the "driving force" for water-diffusion. Assuming that the salt-rejection is 100%, it is possible to write,

$$(\partial \mu_w / \partial x)_M = V_w (\partial P / \partial x)_M \quad \dots (2)$$

where V_w is the molar volume of water, and $(\partial P / \partial x)_M$ is the pressure gradient applied across the membrane (in reality, it is the effective pressure gradient across the membrane).

It follows from equations (1) and (2),

$$J_w = -D_w \frac{C_w V_w}{RT} (\partial P / \partial x)_M \quad \dots (3)$$

If now ρ_m is the density (g. cm^{-3}) of "water solution" (which is dilute) in the membrane-matrix,

then

$$C_w \cong \frac{t_w \rho_m}{M_w} \quad \dots (4)$$

where t_w is the weight-fraction of water in the membrane, and M_w is the molecular weight of water.

Therefore, from equations (3) and (4),

$$J_w \cong -D_w \frac{t_w \rho_m V_w}{RT M_w} (\partial P / \partial x)_M \quad \dots (5)$$

Assuming for a dilute solution,

$$\frac{\rho_m V_w}{M_w} \cong 1 \quad \dots (6)$$

equation (5) becomes

$$J_w \cong -D_w \frac{t_w}{RT} (\partial P / \partial x)_M \quad \dots (7)$$

On the assumption that the pressure gradient in the membrane is linear, one obtains from equation (7),

$$J_w \cong -D_w \frac{t_w}{RT} (\Delta P / d)_M \quad \dots (8)$$

where d is the *effective* thickness of the membrane, and ΔP , the pressure difference across it.

It follows from equation (8),

$$d \cong D_w \frac{t_w}{RT} (\Delta P / J_w)_M \quad \dots (9)$$

(Omitting the negative sign, which merely indicates the direction of the flux with respect to the pressure gradient)

From literature³, some rough estimates of various parameters of equation (9) may be used for the evaluation of d .

$$J_w = 18.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ g. cm}^{-2} \text{ sec}^{-1} = 1.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol. cm}^{-2} \text{ sec}^{-1};$$

$$P = 100 \text{ atmosphere (which acts across } d, \text{ the effective thickness of the membrane } M);$$

$$D_w = 1.0 \times 10^{-6} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ sec}^{-1};$$

$$R = 0.082 \text{ litre-atmosphere. A}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1};$$

$$T = 300 \text{ A};$$

So, one obtains, on these substitutions, from equation (9),

$$d = \frac{1.0 \times 10^{-6} t_w \times 1.0 \times 10^2}{0.082 \times 10^3 \times 300 \times 1.0 \times 10^{-4}} \text{ cm}$$

$$\text{or, } d = \frac{t_w}{2.4} \times 10^{-4} \text{ cm}$$

$$= (t_w / 2.4) \text{ micron} \quad \dots (10)$$

In such membranes, t_p is of the order 0.2, and hence, from equation (10),

$$d \cong 0.1 \text{ micron,}$$

which is in good agreement with the postulated thickness³ of the dense surface-layer of such membranes.

References

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Kinetics and Mechanism of Alkaline Hexacyanoferrate(III) Oxidation of Levulinic Acid

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THE earlier studies on alkaline hexacyanoferrate(III) oxidation of the organic compounds showed that the anions derived from the organic acids are oxidised by hexacyanoferrate(III) ion¹. However, Speakman and Waters² have suggested complex mechanism for the oxidation of aldehydes, ketones and paraffins. Singh and co-workers³ suggested that the oxidation of formaldehyde takes place by free radical mechanism. The present study aims at getting more definite information regarding the mechanism of oxidation of levulinic acid by alkaline hexacyanoferrate(III).

Experimental

The sample of levulinic acid was of E. Merck grade and all other chemicals were of G.R. (S. Merck). The rate of oxidation was determined titrimetrically³.

Stoichiometry :

The equivalents of hexacyanoferrate(III) required per mole of levulinic acid were found to be four. The acetic and formic acids were identified chromatographically. The stoichiometry of the reaction may be given as

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Results

The results obtained under different conditions are reported in Table 1. The constant value of pseudo first order rate constant shows that the order with respect to hexacyanoferrate(III) is one. Pseudo first order rate constants obtained at different concentrations of both levulinic acid and hydroxide ion were directly proportional to the concentrations of levulinic acid and hydroxide ion respectively showing thereby first order dependence of the reaction on each levulinic acid and hydroxide ion. This is also confirmed by constant values of $k_1/[\text{OH}^-][\text{Substrate}]$ given in the last column of the table. The work has been carried out at three more temperatures and results are given in Table 1. The effect of ionic strength of the medium was also studied and results are given in the table. The energy of activation was found to be 12.1 K cal mol⁻¹.

TABLE I—EFFECT OF VARYING [REACTANTS] ON REACTION RATE

Temp. °C	10 ³ [Fe(CN) ₆ ³⁻] M	10 ³ [LA] M	10 ³ [OH ⁻] M	(μ) M	10 ³ k ₁ min ⁻¹	k ₁ K M ⁻² min ⁻¹
35	1.25	2.00	3.20	0.07	0.76	—
35	1.44	2.00	3.20	0.07	0.79	—
35	1.66	2.00	3.20	0.07	0.76	—
35	2.00	2.00	3.20	0.07	0.73	—
35	2.50	2.00	3.20	0.07	0.69	—
35	3.34	2.00	3.20	0.07	0.73	—
35	4.00	2.00	3.20	0.07	0.71	—
35	2.00	2.00	3.20	0.10	1.06	—
35	2.00	2.00	3.20	0.125	1.40	—
35	2.00	2.00	3.20	0.20	2.00	—
35	2.00	2.00	3.20	0.25	2.44	—
35	2.00	2.00	3.20	0.30	2.76	—
35	2.00	0.80	3.20	0.125	0.60	2.30
35	2.00	1.00	3.20	0.125	0.72	2.25
35	2.00	1.25	3.20	0.125	0.96	2.40
35	2.00	1.40	3.20	0.125	1.10	2.45
35	2.00	1.60	3.20	0.125	1.18	2.34
35	2.00	2.00	3.20	0.125	1.53	2.39
35	2.00	3.00	3.20	0.125	2.28	2.37
35	2.00	2.00	2.50	0.125	1.15	2.55
35	2.00	2.00	4.00	0.125	1.90	2.37
35	2.00	2.00	5.00	0.125	2.28	2.28
35	2.00	2.00	6.66	0.125	3.24	2.43
35	2.00	2.00	10.00	0.125	4.86	2.43
30	1.25	2.00	3.20	0.07	0.47	—
40	1.25	2.00	3.20	0.07	1.12	—
45	1.25	2.00	3.20	0.07	1.70	—

LA → Levulinic Acid.

Discussion

In the light of above observations, the probable